

Adequate Early Treatment of a Complex Knee Injury with Options for The Treatment of Complications-Case Report.

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ABSTRACT

Complex knee injuries are most common among the young population and they are very challenging to treat. They are the result of high energy trauma. We present a 33- year old male who was injured in a car crash and suffered a complex knee injury. He sustained a multiligament knee injury with open fracture of medial femoral condyle, multifragmentary fracture of patella and fracture of lateral tibial condyle with bone defect. First operation was performed 1 hour after hospital admission: wound irrigation, osteosynthesis of medial femoral condyle, lateral tibial condyle osteosynthesis, osteosynthesis of patella, posterior cruciate ligament repair and patellar ligament sutures. 20 weeks after, knee joint was in severe contracture. Afterwards, two arthroscopic adhesyolyses were done and osteosynthetic materials were removed. After one more cycle of physical therapy, results were satisfactory: knee extension was full, maximal flexion was 130 degrees.

Keywords: Complex knee injuries; Distal femur fracture; Proximal tibia fracture

INTRODUCTION

Juxta- and intraarticular fractures of the knee (floating knee), intraarticular fractures with severe soft tissue damage and knee dislocations with vascular or soft tissue lesions are defined as complex knee trauma [1]. Young, male patients involved in motor vehicle accidents are risk factors for knee dislocations and their associated injuries, such as neurological injuries, amputations and compartment syndrome. Vascular injury occurs at a frequency of around 15% [2].

A specific management protocol is required for these cases. Fractures should be treated with soft-tissue sparing minimal invasive reduction and fixation techniques to reduce the significant complication rate which is nowadays still often encountered. Percutaneous plate fixation, percutaneous screw osteosynthesis and hybrid fixation should be widely used in these cases. In knee dislocation, the central pivot with the two cruciate ligaments should be reconstructed using augmented repair or primary tendon grafting in every case, whereas the treatment of collateral ligament lesions depends on the specific injury type [1]. Repair of the collaterals is usually reserved for bony avulsions that are large enough to be fixed with hardware or suture anchors [3].

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Fracture-dislocations of the knee are severe injuries that have frequently been associated with poor outcomes. The most common fracture around the knee associated with a multiligament knee injury is a tibial plateau fracture. It is difficult to treat patients who have instability of both the bone (a fracture) and ligaments of the knee. (4) The initial evaluation of these injuries should include a thorough patient history and physical examination, with particularly close attention to vascular status which has the most immediate treatment implications. (5) This is a case report of a 33-year-old male who was injured in a car crash and had a complex open knee injury.

CASE REPORT

A 33-year-old man was admitted to our surgical emergency department following a car accident- he had crashed into a truck. There was no record of loss of consciousness, although partial anterograde amnesia was noted. At initial evaluation his vital signs were stable, GCS 15. The dominant injuries were multiple open fractures of the left knee (Figure 1), with absent arterial pulsations distally. Also, the primary survey revealed a head injury with a laceration of the left eyelid, pain in the lower left quadrant of the abdomen and signs of an injury to the left hand. After the standard blood tests were taken, whole body MSCT was performed and showed fracture of medial femoral condyle, multifragmentary fracture of patella and fracture of lateral tibial condyle with bone defect. Also, MSCT angiography of left leg was performed and the test excluded arterial injury (Figure 2). After the diagnostic tests were done, patient was transferred to the operating room.

Figure 1: Wound on left knee, exposed bones.

Figure 2: Preoperative CT scan of a left knee.

Operation was performed in regional spinal anesthesia. The wounds were irrigated first and foreign bodies were removed. Knee joint and fractures were irrigated with large amounts of 0,9% saline. Soft tissue coverage was adequate and wound closure without tension was possible, so the surgeon decided to do the definitive fixation of fractures and ligaments repair. Intraoperatively multifragmentary fracture of lateral tibial condyle with bone defect; rupture of anterior cruciate (LCA) and posterior cruciate (PCL) ligament; multifragmentary fracture of patella with bone defect in distal part; multifragmentary fracture of medial femoral condyle with loose osteochondral fragment (approximately 1x3cm) and partial rupture of medial part of patellar ligament were found. After the reduction of fractured lateral tibial condyle, percutaneous fixation with cancellous screws and one cortical screw was performed. Afterwards, remaining parts of PCL were sutured and anterior horn of lateral meniscus was sutured to the tibia. Due to poor quality of anterior cruciate ligament tissue, repair of anterior cruciate ligament was not performed. Fracture of medial femoral condyle was reduced under intraoperative X-ray control and percutaneous fixation with cancellous screws was performed. Loose osteochondral fragment was fixated with two cancellous screws. Patella was reconstructed and fixation with small cancellous screws and cerclage wire was performed. Patellar ligament was reconstructed with Krackow transosseal stitches (Figure 3). After the operational procedure, above the knee splint was administered.

Figure 3: Postoperative X-ray image of the left knee.

During the 8-day stay in the hospital, antibiotics (cefuroxime 3x1,5g i.v. /24h and metronidazol 3x500mg i.v. /24h), low molecular heparin thromboprophylaxis (dalteparin 5000 IU sc. /24h) and analgesics were administered to the patient. Early mobilization with two forearm crutches started immediately.

3 weeks after operation signs of inflammation of the postoperative wound (redness, serous exudation) were noted. The swabs were taken and sent to microbiological analysis, which came back sterile.

6 weeks after the operation, immobilization was taken off and physical therapy started. X-rays showed proper position of implants and fracture fragments.

20 weeks after the operation, despite the intensive physical therapy, knee joint was in severe contracture: loss of extension 15-20 degrees, maximal flexion 45 degrees. The patient was suggested to undergo the arthroscopic adhesiolysis.

4 months after the arthroscopic adhesiolysis was done, the patient had 20 degrees extension deficiency and the maximal knee flexion was 80 degrees.

5 months after the first adhesiolysis, readhesiolysis was done. Also, osteosynthetic materials from patella, femur and tibia were removed, posterior capsulotomy and releasing of lateral head of m. gastrocnemius were performed. The patient underwent one more cycle of physical therapy and the final results were satisfactory: knee extension was full and maximal flexion of the left knee was 130 degrees (Figure 4,5). The patient had hypotrophy of the left quadriceps muscle (Figure 6). Lysholm knee score was 89.

Figure 4: Extension 28 months after injury.

Figure 5: Flexion 28 months after injury

Figure 6: Hypotrophy of the left quadriceps muscle 28 months after injury.

DISCUSSION

This case report demonstrates a successful treatment of the complex knee joint trauma type 2 (according to the Krettek C. *et al* [6]).

There are only a few similar cases of the complex knee trauma described in literature, [7, 8] so there is no universal algorithm to treat this type of complex knee joint injuries. First step of our treatment was evaluation of vascular status of the patient. After the vascular injury was excluded, we forwarded the patient to the OR to treat the open knee joint fractures. In our case, we took care of the soft tissues through minimal invasive percutaneous screw fixations of fractured bones. Also, primary repair of posterior cruciate ligament ensured stability of the knee joint. ACL was not repaired during first operation due to poor ligament tissue quality. Afterwards, ACL reconstruction was not performed because postoperative stiffness of the knee joint ensured satisfactory stability of the joint [10]. Also, we tried to reconstruct the knee joint anatomically (avoiding patellectomy). With prompt diagnostics, administration of iv. antibiotics and irrigation in the OR, postoperative infection was avoided. Good and intensive postoperative physical therapy and two arthroscopic adhesiolyses were needed to regain normal range of movement [9].

CONCLUSION

Treatment of complex knee injuries, as shown in this case report, is not a simple and brief process. It demands well-timed multiple surgical interventions, intensive physical therapies and long recovery period. The best management strategy for these injuries remains unclear due to the paucity of high-level evidence. Prospective, randomized studies involving multiple centres are likely required to produce more definite conclusions [11].

REFERENCES

1. Lobenhoffer P, Krettek C, Tschern H. Complex knee trauma. Orthopade 1997; 26(12):1037-1045.
2. Chowdhry M, Burchette D, Whelan D, Nathens A, Marks P, Wasserstein D. Knee dislocation and associated injuries: an analysis of the American College of Surgeons National Trauma Data Bank. Knee surgery, sports traumatology, arthroscopy. 2020;28(2):568-575.
3. Moatshe Gilbert, Jorge Chahla, Marc J. Strauss, Robert F. LaPrade, Lars Engebretsen, et al. Advances in Treatment of Complex Knee Injuries." ESSKA Instructional Course Lecture Book: Glasgow 2018;2018:1-13.
4. Fanelli Gregory C, Stannard, James P, Stuart Michael, MacDonald Peter B, Marx Robert G, Whelan Daniel B, et al. Management of Complex Knee Ligament Injuries. J Bone Joint Surg Am. 2010;92(12): 2235-2246.
5. Ockuly AC, Imada AO, Richter DL, Treme GP, Wascher DC, Schenck Jr, RC. Initial evaluation and classification of knee dislocations. Sports Med Arthrosc Rev. 2020;28(3):87-93.
6. Krettek C, Schandelmaier P, Lobenhoffer P, Tschern H. Complex trauma of knee joint. Diagnosis-- management-- therapeutic principles. Unfallchirurg. 1996;99(9):616-27.
7. Wu CM, Liao HE, Lan SJ. Simultaneous bilateral floating knee: A case report. World J Clin Cases. 2022;10(28):10172-10179.
8. Tahami Mohammad, Vaziri Arash, Tahmasebi Mohammad, Vosoughi Fardis, Khalilzad Majid, Safari Rasool. Multi-Ligament Knee Injury with Concomitant Tibial Tubercle Fracture: A Challenging Case Report and Review of the Pertinent Literature. Journal of Orthopedic and Spine Trauma. 2021;6.
9. Pujol N, Boisrenoult P, Beaufils P. Post-traumatic knee stiffness: Surgical techniques. Orthop Traumatol Surg Res. 2015;101(1):179-186.
10. Meuffels DE, Poldervaart MT, Diercks RL, Fievez AW, Patt TW, Hart CP, et al. Guideline on anterior cruciate ligament injury. Acta Orthop. 2012;83(4):379-86.
11. Ng JWG, Myint Y, Ali FM. Management of multiligament knee injuries. EFORT Open Rev. 2020;5(3):145-155.